

Major Air Pollutants

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Even though air pollution has existed for generations, both the definition of pollution and the classification of a substance as a pollutant are in Transition. The definition of pollution has been evolving at an incredible rate. Although carbon dioxide was not classified among the primary air pollutants in the 1970s, it is now universally recognized that it has a significant impact on ecosystems. Nowadays, not only increased concentration of carbon dioxide is considered a pollutant but there are many other air pollutants like sulfur dioxide, nitrogen oxide, carbon oxides, particulate matter, volatile organic compounds, etc. Now we are going to discuss a few pollutants.

Sulfur Dioxide

Sulfur dioxide is a corrosive gas that originates from the burning of fuels (oil & coal). It's a respiratory irritant that also has the potential to harm plant tissue. Because Sulphur is present in varying proportions in all plants and animals, but Sulphur is present (a substantial amount) in the fossil fuels produced from their remains. The Sulphur in these fuels reacts with oxygen to generate Sulphur dioxide when they are burned. Sulfur dioxide is also released in significant amounts during volcanic eruptions and, though in much smaller amounts, during forest fires. Combustion of fuel containing Sulphur in it is one of the major sources of Sulphur production. As I have already described that

Sulphur dioxide is a respiratory irritant, and it can make asthma worse. In humans, Sulphur dioxide can harm the stomach and in plants, it can damage plant tissues. Sulfur dioxide is an acid rain constituent, during rain (in the presence of water it turns into sulfuric acid by oxidation reaction. This sulfuric acid is harmful to aquatic life and vegetation.

Nitrogen Oxides

Generally, we write nitrogen oxides as NO_X, here X represents that nitrogen is having one or two oxygen with it. If it has only one oxygen then it is called nitrogen oxide (NO) which is an odorless and colorless gas. When nitrogen has two oxygen with it NO₂ then we know it as nitrogen dioxide which has a pungent smell and is reddish-brown in color. Now there is no need to be confused it's clear that when we use the term nitrogen oxides then it includes both nitrogen oxide and nitrogen dioxide. They both are present in the atmosphere they can transform from one form to another forms.

There are many sources for the production of nitrogen oxides. There are two types of sources of nitrogen oxides production. One is anthropogenic sources and the others are natural sources. Anthropogenic sources include fossil fuel burning. And natural sources include microbial action in soil, lightning, and forest fires. The presence of nitrogen oxides in the

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atmosphere is a major reason for the production of ozone below the stratosphere.

Oxides of nitrogen are respiratory irritants and increase the chances to get respiratory infections. The presence of ozone below the stratosphere is the reason for the production of the smog (photochemical smog). Oxides of nitrogen can form nitric acid which is harmful to aquatic life and vegetation also.

Carbon Oxides

The incomplete combustion of fossil fuel produces carbon monoxide which is an odorless and colorless gas. Carbon monoxide is one of the main constituents of air pollution in urban areas. And it is one of the most important indoor air pollutants. Carbon monoxide is bound to haemoglobin and interferes with oxygen transport in the bloodstream. “Causes headaches in humans at low concentrations: can cause death with prolonged exposure at high concentrations”. But on the other hand, carbon monoxide also has positive impacts on the plants like root development, seed germination, and stomatal closure. And carbon monoxide increases the ability of the plants to bear the abiotic stresses through the enhancement of the antioxidant defence system.

Carbon dioxide is also produced from the complete combustion of fuel, it's a colorless and odorless gas. We all know that plants intake carbon dioxide from the environment and in return, they produce oxygen and release it back to the atmosphere. It's a beneficial process. In general, the complete combustion of matter that produces carbon dioxide is more desirable than the incomplete combustion that produces carbon monoxide and other pollutants. But the excessive amount of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere is dangerous, excessive burning of fuels brings him in the category of pollutants. Carbon dioxide causes the alteration in the climate and ecosystem by increasing greenhouse gas concentrations. Carbon dioxide is the reason behind the increase in the temperature of the earth and the melting of glaciers.

Particulate Matter

Particulate matters are solid or liquid particles suspended in the air. Particulate matter comes from the

combustion of animal manure, wood, biofuels, oil, gasoline, and coal. These pollutants are mainly considered as the production of oil and coal burning. Particulate matter can also come from the roads (in the form of dust), volcanoes, dust storms, forest fires.

Particulate matters are of different sizes based on their sizes these particles travel long distances. Their size ranges from 0.01 micro-meter to 100 micro-meter. There are three types of particulate matter coarse particles, fine particles, and ultra-fine particles. Ultra-fine particles can travel and enter in human lungs.

Particulate matters make humans susceptible to respiratory infections and cardiovascular diseases. And reduces lung functions. May lead to premature death. Reduces visibility, and contributes to haze and smog.